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Grant Report

The COST Short-term Scientific Mission (COST action no. CA21134, grant no. E-COST-GRANT-CA21134-614dc773) was carried out as planned, between 14 April and 11 May 2024, at the Instituto Superior de Agronomia in Lisbon, Portugal, under the supervision of Prof. Elisabete Figueiredo. Additional contributors to the internship were Prof. José Carlos Franco and Dr Robin Payne. The title of the internship was: "The effect of companion plants on pest and beneficial insect population in greenhouse tomato production".

During my internship, I was primarily involved in research carried out as part of the PRIMA ASTER project "Agroecology-inspired strategies and tools to enhance resilience and ecosystem services in tomato crop". In brief, the research part of the project carried out in Portugal consists of assessing the impact of implementing companion plants (*Rosmarinus prostratus*, *Borago officinalis*, *Viburnum tinus*, *Thymus mastichina*, *Helichrysum italicum*, *Coriandrum sativum*, *Lavandula stoechas*, *Calendula arvensis*, *Lobularia maritima*, *Ononis ramosissima*, *Calluna vulgaris*, *Foeniculum vulgare*, *Phacelia tanacetifolia*) in greenhouse tomato production on pest and beneficial insect populations, including natural enemies of pests and pollinating insects. As intended, the companion plants are to increase functional biodiversity, thereby facilitating pest management and increasing yield and its quality through enhanced pollination.

The ASTER experimental site is located in Silveira, about 60 km north-west of Lisbon. There is a greenhouse complex where tomatoes are grown, and where the biodiversity-enhancing practices are being implemented. The area around the study site is semi-urban, with some small crop fields, some small eucalyptus plantations, and a significant number of

other small to medium size greenhouse operations. Entomofauna biodiversity surveys are carried out using Malaise traps (Figure 1) and pan traps, placed outside the greenhouses. Insect sampling covers the period from May to November. A bird's-eye view of the experiment site, with the sampling points marked, is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. An example of Malaise traps in place between greenhouses (EST8-MT1 and EST8-MT2)

In the first year of the study (2023), the primary aim was to use the Malaise traps to capture representative insect samples, prior to introduction of an “ASTER production system” in the following year (2024). Entomofauna samples collected in 2023 were stored in ethanol solution for identification.

As the planting period of tomatoes and companion plants in the greenhouses was delayed for reasons beyond the responsibility of the intern and the hosts, after close scrutiny of the experimental layout, my main task was to identify the last year's samples. I was focused on distinguishing between insects of the order Hymenoptera, initially dividing the numerous individuals caught into the following classes: bees, parasitic wasps, other wasps. After this initial classification, instructed by the hosts and equipped with the relevant literature, I have classified the parasitic wasps in the family Ichneumonidae (subfamilies: Ichneumonidae and Braconidae), and other taxa within the parasitic Hymenoptera (Proctotrupidae, Chrysididae, Chalcididae). The classification was carried out based on the morphological traits of the insects (wing venation, structure of trochanters and antennae,

presence of an elongated ovipositor, typical of parasitic wasps; Figures 3 and 4). Throughout my work I was supported by the hosts and the results were regularly verified.

Figure 2. The location of Greenhouse 5 (EST5, the Control) and Greenhouse 8 (EST8, the ASTER Treatment), the 8 Malaise traps (MTs) and the 12 sets of blue, yellow and white pan traps (PTs)

The work I have done is a significant contribution to the ASTER project, providing a basis for comparing the richness and abundance of beneficial arthropods in the next years of the research on the biodiversity-enhancing practices. The results on Braconidae and Ichneumonidae obtained by me during the internship are presented in Table 1.

Figure 3. An example of a parasitic wasp in the subfamily Ichneumonidae. The forewing shows a distinctive venation. The discal and the second submarginal cells form the discosubmarginal cell with a shape called “horse head”

Figure 4. An example of a parasitic wasp in the subfamily Braconidae

Table 1. Numbers of specimens in Braconidae and Ichneumonidae subfamilies, caught in Silveira (Portugal) in the year 0 of the research performed within the ASTER project

Date	Sample ID	Number of specimens	
		Ichneumonidae	Braconidae
29 V – 1 VI 2023	EST8 – MT1	25	3
29 V – 1 VI 2023	EST8 – MT2	64	17
29 V – 1 VI 2023	EST8 – MT3	26	16
29 V – 1 VI 2023	EST8 – MT4	166	34
29 V – 1 VI 2023	EST5 – MT5	22	6
29 V – 1 VI 2023	EST5 – MT6	21	8
29 V – 1 VI 2023	EST5 – MT7	37	7
29 V – 1 VI 2023	EST5 – MT8	24	10
4 – 7 VII 2023	EST8 – MT1	35	21
4 – 7 VII 2023	EST8 – MT2	17	11
4 – 7 VII 2023	EST8 – MT3	49	24
4 – 7 VII 2023	EST8 – MT4	11	16
4 – 7 VII 2023	EST5 – MT5	18	10
4 – 7 VII 2023	EST5 – MT6	12	12
4 – 7 VII 2023	EST5 – MT7	21	7
4 – 7 VII 2023	EST5 – MT8	19	6
12 – 15 IX 2023	EST8 – MT1	18	9
12 – 15 IX 2023	EST8 – MT2	8	12
12 – 15 IX 2023	EST8 – MT3	19	33
12 – 15 IX 2023	EST8 – MT4	21	22
12 – 15 IX 2023	EST5 – MT5	26	17
12 – 15 IX 2023	EST5 – MT6	0	0
12 – 15 IX 2023	EST5 – MT7	16	7
12 – 15 IX 2023	EST5 – MT8	5	2
12 IX 2023	yellow tube MT5	9	5
21 – 24 XI 2023	EST8 – MT1	3	2
21 – 24 XI 2023	EST8 – MT2	2	7
21 – 24 XI 2023	EST8 – MT3	11	28
21 – 24 XI 2023	EST8 – MT4	1	1
21 – 24 XI 2023	EST5 – MT5	1	0
21 – 24 XI 2023	EST5 – MT6	1	1
21 – 24 XI 2023	EST5 – MT7	11	16
21 – 24 XI 2023	EST5 – MT8	3	0

Moreover, during the internship in Portugal, I also had the opportunity to learn about and to participate in other research carried out at the Instituto Superior de Agronomia. Particularly worth mentioning is the CRI-CRI project, which focuses on finding efficient forage sources for intensive cricket rearing.

In summary, within the STSM in Portugal, I achieved the following goals important for my scientific development:

- i. getting to know the latest taxonomy of parasitic wasps and learning to recognise particular families and subfamilies (This is a valuable skill that I will use in my future scientific work. There are no parasitic wasp specialists in my home institution, so Prof. Figueiredo's high level of expertise in this area was of great help to me);
- ii. improving my bee identification skills, which I will use in my doctoral research (thanks to Dr Robin Payne, bee specialist);
- iii. learning about pests that threaten crops in southern Europe, which, due to the climate change, may also appear in Poland.

The internship in Portugal also allowed me to establish strong scientific relationships that will be useful for possible further cooperation in the field of sustainable agricultural production. Furthermore, in order to address another objective of the TOP-AGRI-Network, which is to gather and disseminate interdisciplinary knowledge in the field of agroecological bases of crop management, a review scientific paper on the effect of biodiversity-enhancing practices on pollinator populations in agroecosystems is being prepared in cooperation, and will have been published in the Journal of Apicultural Science by the end of the year (appendix 1).

*Yours sincerely,
Gerard Podchowaty*

The use of companion plants to support pollinator populations and enhance pollination services in crops: a review (The introduction of floral resources to...?)

Higher pollinator insect diversity makes agroecosystems more resilient to negative effects of climate change on flower pollination, i.e. phenological mismatch between early-spring blooming crop plants and pollinator insect activity. The presence of diverse groups of pollinating insects having different adaptability to environmental changes increases the likelihood of pollinator-crop synchrony (Bartomeus et al., 2013).

Wild bees (including most crop-visiting species) can adapt to agriculturally transformed landscapes by using complementary habitats throughout the season. They use fallow areas early in the season, crops mid-season, and neglected fields later in the season. Nearby forests are less important and mainly visited by non-crop pollinator species (Mandelik et al., 2012).

The adjacent flower strips have a beneficial effect on the growth and reproduction of bumblebee colonies (Klatt et al., 2020).

In addition to nesting sites and food resources, perennial flowering habitats provide also overwintering habitats for wild pollinators in intensive agricultural landscapes (Boetze et al., 2022).

Proper selection of species in flower strips can provide different groups of pollinating insect with forage even during natural periods of its deficiency (Benelli et al., 2014).

Pollinator abundance on agricultural fields depends on both landscape and crop context. However, the influence of these factors has different significance for the individual pollinator groups, which should be considered separately. One of the most important characteristics of a crop is the temporal overlap between its flowering period and pollinator activity (demand) (Brandt et al., 2017).

Delphia et al. (2019) demonstrate that wild flower strips established for wild bee conservation can also generate additional income when their seeds are harvested and sold to individual clients. This could be a promising incentive for farmers to implement pollinator-friendly practices.

Pollinators may react differently to the size of flower strips. In a study by Blaauw & Isaacs (2014b), honey bees and hoverflies did not respond to wildflower patch size. In general, the density and diversity of wild bees increased with increasing wildflower patch area in the range of 1-100 m², irrespective of bloom period throughout the season. The positive correlation between wildflower patch size and wild bee density was confirmed for taxonomic groups such as *Bombus* spp., Andrenidae, Halictidae and “other Apidae”, with the exception of Megachilidae, which did not respond to wildflower patch area. On the contrary, Heard et al. (2007) did not find the density of bumble bees visiting sown flower strips to be significantly affected by their size. Instead, changes in bumble bee density were linked to landscape context, i.e. in areas with a high proportion of agricultural production, where mass-flowering crop species provide pollinators with forage only periodically, bumble bees visit flower strips in greater numbers in search of a food source. The non-interaction of the size of flower strips on the bumble bee and honey bee density and on bumble bee species richness in red clover fields was also shown by Rundlöf et al. (2018).

Holzschuh et al. (2007), comparing organic and conventional cereal fields under different landscape conditions and in different regions, found that the organic production system favours more abundant and diverse flower cover, and this has a major and direct impact on flower-visiting bee diversity. The influence of landscape effects was of lesser importance, but both landscape and regional perspectives should not be ignored in studies of local bee diversity. In turn, Geppert et al. (2020) reported both the organic production system and establishing flower strips adjacent to conventional fields to be effective methods of increasing pollinator local richness and abundance in cereal crops. Both methods also improved the development and reproduction of bumble bee colonies, but depending on the size of the field. The most favourable for bumble bees were small conventional fields with flower strips or large organic fields where the floral resources were spread over the entire field area. On the contrary, Chanteil

& Porcher (2015) point to the dominant role of landscape context in shaping pollination services, compared to agricultural practice (organic vs. conventional farming). Visitation rates by pollinators of *Lotus corniculatus* flowers, the obligate insect-pollinated indicator plant, and fruit production, were positively correlated with the presence of semi-natural habitats in the surrounding area, but did not differ according to the agricultural practice.

The number of flower-visiting insects within winter cereal and mixed-crop fields was higher in the organic than in the conventional production system (Couthouis et al., 2023).

Schoch et al. (2022) found that the total abundance of pollinating insects and the abundance and diversity of wild bees in flower strips were negatively correlated with the proportion of semi-natural farmland habitats in the landscape within a 1 km radius. This suggests the phenomenon of competition and dilution of pollinator populations in the landscape. On the other hand, surrounding habitats with high botanical biodiversity had a positive effect on pollinator abundance in the strips. Therefore, it was suggested that the highest effectiveness in attracting pollinators would be achieved by flower strips in landscapes of low to medium complexity, but with high ecological quality of existing semi-natural habitats.

The abundance of wild bees in flower strips was positively correlated with the proportion of semi-natural habitats within 500 m, but negatively with the presence of forest. No such correlation was found for hoverflies (Albrecht et al., 2021).

According to Cano et al. (2022), the abundance and diversity of pollinating insects within olive groves depended on the floral richness of the strips, but not on the level of agricultural intensification in the surrounding area or the landscape complexity. Similarly, landscape context did not affect pollination services (*Sinapis alba* used as an indicator).

The effectiveness of flower strips may also be affected by the scale of agricultural production within the farm or the diversity of species grown. It should be noted that most of the research has been undertaken on large-scale and specialised farms. However, on smaller farms, diversified in terms of crops grown and often characterised by a more extensive production system, the pollinator population may already be sufficiently abundant and diverse that the establishment of floral strips does not provide a measurable benefit (Delphia et al., 2022).

The increasing flower density in strips favours the overall abundance of pollinating insects and wild bees (Schoch et al., 2022). A strong positive correlation was observed between the flowering plant species richness and the abundance of hoverflies and wild bees in flower strips (Albrecht et al., 2021).

Potts et al. (2009), taking into consideration the decline in pollinator diversity in intensively managed grasslands, decided to study the effect of two mixtures of plants sown into the sward (a cereal, grass and legume mix or a conservation mix with kale, cereals, linseed and legumes) on the abundance and species diversity of bumble bees and butterflies. In sites where the plant mixtures were sown, the higher abundance and species richness of bumble bees was observed, while in the grass-based sites they were almost absent. The mixture containing more flowering species (especially leguminous) favoured the higher abundance and greater species diversity of bumble bees. As for butterflies, they were found in greater numbers and diversity on sites where plant mixtures were sown or where the most extensive grassland management was practised. However, butterfly larvae were most abundant in grass sites where no reseeding of flowering species was applied. The increase in bumble bee abundance and diversity was linked to enhanced floral species richness and nectar resources. The higher abundance of adult butterflies was associated with the increase in flower abundance, whilst butterfly species richness was correlated with the higher floral species richness. The butterfly occurrence was mainly favoured by the presence of flowering nectar plants other than legumes, higher than 20 cm and therefore providing good shelter (e.g. *Cirsium*, *Ranunculus*, *Senecio*, *Veronica*). However, the grass-based sites provided a better environment for butterfly larvae, probably due to the greater availability of suitable host plants for oviposition (e.g. *Agrostis*, *Lolium*, *Holcus*).

A comparative study by Haaland & Bersier (2011) showed higher abundance but not species richness of butterflies in flower strips compared to extensively used meadows. Within the flower strips, species of the genus *Origanum* were the most attractive to butterflies (65% of all flower visits).

Practices to enhance the proportion of flowering plants in buffer grass strips have increased butterfly abundance and species richness (Blake et al., 2011).

Five years of observations confirmed an increase in species richness of wild bees and butterflies in cereal-dominated agricultural areas, where flower strips with about 10 per cent of the landscape were implemented. In addition, endangered bee species that were absent from conventional production areas were found in areas of biodiversity-enhancing practices (Buhk et al., 2018).

In an agricultural area with grass cultivation, flower strips increased bumblebee abundance and species richness, as well as butterfly diversity, over a four-year period. However, their contribution to insect conservation, as assessed by the presence of habitat specialist butterflies, was more dependent on the landscape context (forest proximity) (Korpela et al., 2013).

Butterfly populations are supported not only by floral resources, but also by butterfly larval foodplants found in green infrastructure sites on agricultural land. Therefore, unmanaged agricultural crop margins provided higher butterfly abundance than hedgerows (Croxtton et al., 2015).

Different flowering plant species do not promote particular groups of pollinators found in agroecosystems in the same degree. Sutter et al. (2017b) studied herbaceous plants from semi-natural sites in Switzerland for their suitability as a source of forage for three main groups of pollinators: (i.) rare and endangered wild bees; (ii.) wild bees commonly found in agricultural crops, and (iii.) honey bees. The study confirmed that the abundance of insects from these three groups is favoured not so much by the overall diversity of flowering plants, but by the presence of the particular flowering species they prefer (i.e. 'key plant species').

The ten plant species most frequently used by honey bees (ordered in descending proportion of visits) were: *Taraxacum officinale*, *Achillea millefolium*, *Knautia arvensis*, *Centaurea jacea*, *Melilotus albus*, *Origanum vulgare*, *Trifolium repens*, *Crepis capillaris*, *Leucanthemum vulgare* and *Trifolium pratense*. For rare and endangered wild bees these were: *Trifolium pratense*, *Taraxacum officinale*, *Vicia sepium*, *Achillea millefolium*, *Centaurea jacea*, *Crepis capillaris*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Knautia arvensis*, *Origanum vulgare*, *Potentilla neummanniana*, whilest for common wild bees: *Trifolium pratense*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Centaurea jacea*, *Taraxacum officinale*, *Rhinanthus alectorolophus*, *Origanum vulgare*, *Hypericum perforatum*, *Vicia sepium*, *Echium vulgare*, *Malva neglecta* (Sutter et al., 2017b).

Analyses of plant-pollinator relationships identified the flowering plant species preferred by each group of pollinators. Some of them overlapped. Two key plant species preferentially visited by bees in all three target groups were *Achillea millefolium* and *Origanum vulgare*. In addition, *A. millefolium* provided an attractive forage for hoverflies, a pollinator family not classified as bees. Both honey bees and common wild bees preferentially visited *Centaurea jacea* and *Medicago sativa*. For honey bees and rare wild bees, *Knautia arvensis* and *Echium vulgare* were common. All pollinator groups also preferentially visited clover, which highlights the role of fabaceous species in preserving beneficial insects, with honey bees preferring *Trifolium repens* and other insect species (especially bumble bees) preferring *T. pratense*. Further plant species preferred by managed honey bees were *Melilotus albus*, *Tanacetum vulgare*, *Centaurea scabiosa* and *Epilobium hirsutum*; by rare wild bees – *Crepis capillaris*; and by wild but common bees – *Lotus corniculatus*, *Hypericum perforatum*, *Malva neglecta* and *Cirsium arvense*. The selection of appropriate key plant species might facilitate the creation of diverse mixtures optimal for the conservation of different groups of bees (Sutter et al., 2017b).

According to Burkle et al. (2020), there were key plant species attracting the greatest overall diversity of wild bees to flower strips in agricultural areas, and their role did not vary considerably with the landscape context. Against the others, *Erigeron speciosus* and *Geranium viscosissimum* received the most visits and attracted the highest species diversity of wild bees. However, supporting rare bee species requires inclusion of specific flowering species, the selection of which may depend on the landscape context. Although their contribution to supporting the overall richness of wild bees may not be significant, they are crucial for the conservation of rare and endangered pollinators.

Similarly, a study on the role of natural soil cover in apple orchards concluded that it is not so much the overall richness but the presence of specific, most rewarding forage plants that matters for pollinator abundance (García & Miñarro, 2014).

Morphological traits of inflorescences of plant species sown in flower strips are of great importance for the activity and diversity of insects attracted. On this basis, the composition of floral mixtures can be selected to promote certain groups of insects. In a study by Campbell et al. (2017b), the floral mixtures were divided into three functional groups: (i.) species that

generally require specialised feeding structures (e.g. long proboscis) to obtain forage, and nectar is produced in deep corollas or spurs, these were: *Centaurea montana*, *Cichorium intybus*, *Hypericum perforatum*, *Knautia arvensis*, *Lamium purpureum*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Medicago sativa*, *Phacelia tanacetifolia*, *Trifolium pratense*, *Trifolium hybridum*, *Trifolium repens*, *Primula veris*, *Clinopodium vulgare*, *Vicia cracca*; (ii.) "open" nectar plants, providing more easily accessible forage from flowers with short corollas or extra-floral nectaries, including: *Fagopyrum esculentum*, *Achillea millefolium*, *Lobularia maritima*, *Foeniculum vulgare*, *Daucus carota*, *Pastinaca sativa*, *Ammi majus*, *Coriandrum sativum*, *Tanacetum vulgare*, *Anethum graveolens*, *Vicia sativa*, *Conopodium majus*; (iii.) a multi-functional mixture, containing all the species previously mentioned. A strong preference was found for particular groups of insects towards the flowering mixtures used – 92.6% of pollinator visits were to species from the first group, while 97.2% of visits by insects considered as natural enemies of pests were to flowers belonging to the second group. Among pollinators, however, solitary bees showed a less pronounced preference for the first mixture (61.7% of visits), which confirms their generalised ability to benefit from diverse floral resources in an agroecosystem. The third, multi-functional flower mix was effective in attracting both pollinators and natural enemies.

Among different species studied, *Silphium integrifolium* and *Silphium perfoliatum* were found most attractive to bees and pollinators in general, with the highest abundance and richness noted. For butterfly abundance and diversity, taken separately, *Medicago sativa* had the most favourable effect (Butters et al., 2022).

Butters et al. (2022) showed a significant positive effect of the amount of floral resources and bloom duration on pollinator abundance.

The high utility of legume mixtures in protecting wild pollinators in agricultural land was reported by Cole et al. (2022). Such plant communities support bumblebee and hoverfly populations, providing them with an ample forage supply. Nevertheless, the use of floral resources by hoverflies, lacking in specialised feeding structures, is limited to flowers with easier access to forage, thus must be supplemented with wild species (e.g. with shallower corollas, open flowers). Another disadvantage of legume-only mixtures in favour of including also species from other botanical families in flower strips, is the limited bloom duration during the season.

In a study by Quinn et al. (2017), flower strips of *Fagopyrum esculentum* or *Brassica hirta* attracted more honey bees and other Apiformes than strips of *Lobularia maritima*. On the contrary, *L. maritima* attracted more hoverflies than *F. esculentum* or *B. hirta*.

Studies on the preference of particular pollinator groups for plant species in flower strips may not provide conclusive results, as was the case with Azpiazu et al. (2020). The preferences varied depending on the year, the season and were influenced by, amongst other factors, the proportion of a species in the floral strip or the number of flowers per plant (higher favoured more frequent visits).

There may be a significant disparity between the attractiveness to pollinators of common weed species and flowering species recommended for mixtures sown on agricultural lands. According to Balfour & Ratnieks (2022), three weed species considered harmful to agricultural production (*Jacobaea vulgaris*, *Cirsium arvense*, *C. vulgare*) were, on average, twice as likely to be visited by pollinating insects than selected species recommended for the mixtures. The weeds were also associated with higher pollinator diversity. This result may be related to their higher nectar productivity (Baude et al., 2016).

The complementary forage role of weeds (in particular *Cirsium*, *Heracleum sphondylium* and *Rubus fruticosus*) in the context of pro-environmental strategies on agricultural land was documented by Crowther & Gilbert (2020).

An important benefit of establishing flower strips may be providing forage for pollinating insect populations also outside the blooming period of cultivated plants. This is particularly important in intensive agricultural production landscapes, where human activity reduces the presence of natural habitats for beneficial insects, thus pollinator foraging is limited to mass-flowering crops (e.g. rape, buckwheat, orchards).

Persistence of plant species in flower strips

When setting the species composition of flower strips, the persistence of plant cover should be considered. A different approach should be taken if flower strips are to be renewed annually,

and another if their use is planned for several years without major interventions. Over time, flower strips can experience changes in their species composition. More expansive plant species displace weaker ones. Some species sow spontaneously. These may include weeds that are of low suitability for pollinators, but which compete with previously sown flowers providing a valuable forage for insects, as well as flowering plants that are beneficial to pollinators.

Based on multilocation observations, Albrecht et al. (2021) recorded severe declines in the abundance of wild bees, honey bees and hoverflies with the length of time since the establishment of flower strips. Already in the second year after sowing, the abundance of the aforementioned pollinator groups in the flower strips decreased by 89%, 62% and 72% respectively. This was linked to a decline in flower density and diversity and an increase in the share of grasses in the strips. "Ageing" of the flower strips observed in this study indicates the need for their regular renewal.

The passage of time since the establishment of flower strips did not affect the abundance of bumblebees or butterflies, whilst honey bees and hoverflies were reported to have declined in abundance. The response of solitary bees, on the other hand, varied between taxa, and so trap-nesting bees did not respond to the 'ageing' of the flower strips, but mining bees declined in abundance (Brittain et al., 2022).

Flower strips were found to be an effective method of increasing a number and diversity of Apidae and hoverflies in wheat crop in an urbanized and intensive agricultural production area. The species composition of the flower strips (i.e. monofloral strips of *Dimorphoteca pluvialis* or *Camelina sativa* and a mixture of 11 flowering plants) did not differentiate the diversity of bee and bumble bee population, but the higher diversity of hoverflies was associated with the multifloral strip (Amy et al., 2018).

Unmanaged hedgerows on the margins of winter cereal fields and weeds present in the crop increased the abundance of the main pollinator groups, with an overriding role of certain plant species shown. Legume intercropping (*Vicia faba* and/or *Pisum sativum*) did not increase the abundance of floral visitors nor improve the already sufficient impact of hedgerows and weeds (Aviron et al., 2023).

Within wildflower strips in the vicinity of wheat fields, higher abundance of hoverflies (larvae and adults, taken together) was found than within spontaneous vegetation or grass strips. The

study was conducted in five locations of different climatic conditions, but fluctuations in hoverfly populations were explained more by differences in floral cover than by climate influence (Bischoff et al., 2022).

Both the functional and species diversity of wild bees was higher in flower strips than in neighbouring sunflower fields (Hevia et al., 2021).

Flower strips can play a complementary role to semi-natural habitats in protecting the species and functional diversity of wild bees in intensive agricultural landscapes (Hevia et al., 2021).

Monofloral strips of *Phacelia tanacetifolia* increased overall bumble bee species richness in red clover fields by 16%, with this beneficial effect observed only when the proportion of arable land in the surrounding landscape did not exceed 50%. This would indicate a stronger impact of flower strips in more heterogeneous landscapes. However, the density of both bumble bees and honey bees in the clover crop was not affected by the presence of the flower strip. When the blooming of the phacelia strips and red clover overlapped, higher densities of both pollinator groups were observed in phacelia, which may suggest a preference towards this species (Rundlöf et al., 2018).

Flower strips in inter-rows of apple orchards increased the abundance of hoverflies and some wild bee species, but not honey nor andrenid bees (Campbell et al., 2017a).

The sowing of multi-species floral mixtures attracted a wide range of pollinating insects, including the honeybee, several species of bumblebees, other wild bees, hoverflies and butterflies. Managing the sowing date ensured the distribution of forage from early summer to late autumn, even beyond the flowering of the crop (Carreck & Williams, 2002).

Replacing wild vegetation at the edges of lowbush blueberry plantations with monofloral strips of *Fagopyrum esculentum* provided no major benefit to the wild bee community richness. As the blooming periods of the strips and the crop did not overlap, the evaluation was carried out separately. Within the flower strips, few individuals of solitary bees from the Megachilidae and Apidae families were found, which did not occur in the unmanaged field margins. In general, however, the genera richness of both plant communities was similar. Wild bee numbers were higher in *F. esculentum* than in wild plants, but only in some years. All bee genera visiting blueberry flowers were also present in the flower strips, which suggests a supportive effect of *F. esculentum* on blueberry flower-pollinating insects. Nevertheless, the beneficial impact of

unmanaged field margins may be sufficient not to justify the implementation of biodiversity enhancing practices (McCallum et al., 2021).

Meek et al. (2002), comparing the usefulness of different practices for maintaining field margins in increasing arthropod biodiversity, found higher abundance of pollinating insects (including bumblebees and butterflies) in those margins that were sown with wildflowers.

Sown flower strips were effective in attracting butterflies and bumblebees in the agricultural landscape, with species belonging to the *Knautia*, *Centaurea* and *Cirsium* genera as the most beneficial. This practice was found to be more effective in supporting wild pollinators than grass-sown and regularly mown greenways (Haaland & Gyllin, 2010).

Critchley et al. (2006) showed that also the establishment of grass strips in arable field margins may be beneficial for pollinating insects. Over time, these habitats are colonised by plant species that provide bumblebees and butterflies with forage resources and favourable conditions for their development cycle.

Venturini et al. (2017) compared three flower treatments (i.e. clovers, various wildflowers and natural regeneration of native plant community) managed as floral strips in lowbush blueberry plantations. It was found that social insects preferred clovers, whilst solitary bees, wildflowers. Native plant patches were the least visited by bees, probably due to the lower flower density. Visits by hoverflies, by contrast, were equally frequent in all flower treatments. No differences in pollinator richness between fields with or without floral treatments were reported. The proportion of pollen from companion plants in bumblebee pollen loads was 37%, indicating that it supplements and replaces pollen of wild plants from natural sites. In another study, a legume-based flowering mixture on field margins attracted higher total number and species richness of bumble bees and bees in general than the natural regeneration. A decline in the attractiveness of natural regeneration was observed over the years, probably due to adverse changes in its floristic composition. A mixture of native wildflowers was also effective in attracting bumblebees, providing greater continuity of forage resources over the season compared to the legume-based mixture (Carvell et al., 2007). Carvell et al. (2004), however, when considering the suitability only for supporting bumblebee populations on arable land, found natural regeneration on field margins to be ineffective in providing continuous forage resources, and proved the advantage of managed margins sown with a mixture of grasses and wildflowers. In contrast, Pywell et al. (2005) consider natural regrowth at field margins to be a beneficial practice for the conservation of bumblebees on arable land, but point out the risk of

the expansion of weeds harmful to agricultural production (e.g. *Cirsium*), which is not as problematic with wildflower seeding.

Floral treatments did not enhance wild bee visits to crop flowers in cherry and blueberry plantations even after five years of the study, but they attracted more diverse and numerous pollinator population themselves compared to control (Wood et al., 2018).

The lack of increase in pollination services, but higher diversity of hoverflies in apple orchards with flower strips in the inter-rows was reported by McKerchar et al. (2020).

An increase in solitary bees, honey bees and bumblebees was observed in apple orchards from the second year after flower strips were established. Hoverflies responded with an increase in abundance already in the first year. There was no effect of landscape context on changes in pollinator populations, although wild bee abundance was positively correlated with the presence of flowering plants in habitats other than flower strips within the orchard (Carvell et al., 2022).

An intercropping practice of sowing sunflower strips within vegetable crops (tomatoes, okra, collards, sweetcorn, watermelons) increased the occurrence of beneficial insects (including pollinators) on crops, with the effect being stronger in the close vicinity of sunflowers (<1 m) than at a distance (10 m from sunflowers). In general, however, beneficial insects were more abundant on sunflowers than on crop plants (Jones & Gillett, 2005).

Although there is relatively abundant data confirming that companion plants increase the biodiversity and density of different pollinator groups in agricultural crops, few studies have documented what effect this has on the pollination and yield of pollinator-dependent crops. In general, it could be hypothesised that: (i.) the presence of companion plants, through the promotion of beneficial insects, increases the proportion of pollinated crop flowers, improving yield quantity and quality; (ii.) companion plants compete with crops for pollinators, and – being more attractive – reduce pollination of crop plants, which negatively affects the yield and its quality; (iii.) there is no significant effect of companion plants on crop pollination.

There is evidence that pollinator species diversity supported by wild vegetation around the crop increases pollination success (Klein et al., 2003).

Wild vegetation at field margins and corners increased the overall yield in an agricultural rotation including oilseed rape, wheat and field beans. The positive impact increased over time

during the 6 years of the experiment and was stronger with a larger area of wild vegetation. The response of particular crop species varied, with the highest yield increases of up to 25-35% recorded for field beans. The loss of production area under biodiversity-enhancing practices was compensated by the increase in crop yield per unit area. The results were linked to higher abundance of honey bees and bumblebees (in bean and oilseed rape trials), but also to more numerous population of selected natural enemies of pests (Pywell et al., 2015).

Rundlöf et al. (2018) found that red clover seed yield was not related to the increase in bee density and diversity noted as an effect of the establishment of monofloral strips of *Phacelia tanacetifolia*, but it increased with increasing size of these strips. Much more promising results were presented by Barbir et al. (2015). In this study, flower resources (monofloral strips of *Diploaxis tenuifolia* or wildflower mix) grown on field margins, not only increased the number of visits by pollinators to the crop's flowers, but also the quality and productivity of coriander seeds by up to 220% compared to the control.

Perennial flower strips established between tree rows increased the visit rate of flies and non-*Apis* bees to apple flowers by 40%, which did not, however, result in an increase in fruit set. Wild pollinator visits to apple flowers were more frequent when there was a semi-natural habitat close to an orchard with flower strips. The visit rate of honey bees did not depend on the presence of flower strips (Campbell et al., 2017a).

Sown flower strips in inter-rows of apple orchards attracted more honey and wild bees than natural ground cover flora. They also favoured a greater taxonomic diversity of wild pollinators. However, this did not increase visits to the apple blossoms (Barda et al., 2023).

Patches of flowering plants sown between trees in an olive grove attracted more honey bees and wild Hymenoptera pollinators (including bumble bees and megachilids) than patches of native vegetation (Karamaouna et al., 2019).

Small patches of perennial native plants established within mango orchards reduced the pesticide-related decline in pollinator abundance and yield. They also increased the diversity and abundance of pollinating insects, thereby increasing the fruit yield in mango orchards distant from clusters of natural vegetation, but still not to the same extent (Carvalho et al., 2012).

Wildflower strips adjacent to highbush blueberry plantations did not affect the honey bee abundance, but they annually increased wild bee and hoverfly numbers to significant levels in

the third and fourth year after their establishment. The enhancement in pollination services increased estimated fruit yields sufficiently to cover expenses of establishing and maintaining the flower strips (Blaauw & Isaacs, 2014a). According to Venturini et al. (2017), over three years of observations on flower treatments in lowbush blueberry, a higher rate of visits to crop flowers by wild bees was found only in the last year, resulting in the increase in fruit set. The estimated increase in revenue from enhanced pollination services covered the cost of investment in floral strips over four years after their establishment. And so another study suggests that it may take several years before floral resources measurably boost pollinator activity in perennial crops.

Monofloral strips of *Fagopyrum esculentum*, *Brassica hirta* or *Lobularia maritima* in cucumber field, although effective in attracting different groups of pollinating insects, generally failed to increase cucumber yield compared to the control where floral strips were not established (significantly higher yield was recorded in only one year of the study, in *L. maritima* treatment). No differences were observed in the abundance of pollinators visiting cucumber flowers (i.e. honey bees, other Apiformes, hoverflies), regardless of the presence, species composition or distance of the flower strips from the crop. This would indicate no dispersal of attracted pollinators from the flower strips, but on the other hand, no competition for pollinators with crop plants. As suggested, the flower strips may have attracted additional pollinators from the surrounding area, without reducing their presence on cucumber flowers (Quinn et al., 2017).

In a study by Azpiazu et al. (2020), multifloral strips attracted more pollinators than melons. They significantly increased the number of pollinators visiting melon flowers, but only in the closest rows (<2 m). As the distance from the flower strips increased, the crop flower visitation rate decreased. This, however, supports the role of flower strips as an exporter of pollinators to adjacent crops. The presence of the flower strips affected neither fruit yield nor quality.

Flower strips along the edges of watermelon fields provided a favourable habitat for bees with positive implications for yield quality. The increase in average fruit weight, improved pollination (reduction in the share of undeveloped seeds) and increased Brix levels were reported (Karamaouna et al., 2022).

Two methods of growing companion plants (i.e. perennial strips adjacent to crops or intercropping vegetables within rows with annual companion plants) were compared in cucumber and habanero pepper production. Habanero pepper yields were significantly increased by annual companion plants in both spring and autumn, whilst cucumber yields only

in autumn. The initially lower yield in the perennial trials was likely due to the attraction of fewer pollinators by the flower strips not yet fully developed. There was no effect of companion plants on fruit quality in any of the crops (Montoya et al., 2020).

Flowers of sweet peppers intercropped with *Ocimum basilicum* were visited by more bee species and in greater abundance than those of peppers grown without the intercrop. Pollinators that were significantly more numerous in the intercropped pepper included honey bee and two local wild bee species. Higher pollinator insect activity in the intercropping system translated into improved fruit pollination (higher number of seeds), increased pepper yield and its commercial quality (wider, longer fruit with higher average weight). This was despite the greater attractiveness of *O. basilicum* to bees, which supports the possibility of sharing the pollinators present in the area between the crop and the companion plant (Pereira et al., 2015). Multispecies flower strips adjacent on both sides to the sweet pepper field increased the occurrence of honey bees on plants in their vicinity to a greater extent than in the central part of the field. This did not translate into differences in plant yield depending on the distance from the flower strips (Lee & Jung, 2019).

Intercropping squash, okra and watermelon with *Vigna unguiculata* increased pollinator abundance and diversity along with vegetable yields (Dingha et al., 2021).

The establishment of wildflower strips increased the abundance of wild bees (but not honey bees) in tomato production. A factor promoting the pollinator population was the increasing floral complexity. Higher yield, number and average fruit weight were obtained from plots adjacent to the flower strips (Balzan et al., 2014; Balzan et al., 2016).

Flower strips of *Calendula officinalis* in field margins were frequently visited by wild bees, with no implications for tomato yield or quality (Balzan, 2017).

Flower strips in tomato field margins proved to be more attractive source of forage for wild bees than native vegetation, while not distracting pollinators from the crop (Kati et al., 2021).

Flower strips in strawberry fields increased pollinator (especially wild bee) activity in adjacent crops, while locally reducing it in the centre of the fields. Overall, strawberry seed set, considered as an indicator of pollination efficiency, did not differ between fields with or without the flower strips. However, within fields where flower strips had been established, significantly more fertile seeds were found in the edges adjacent to the strips than in the centre. Differences in pollinator community preferences were observed. Only 12.5% of the pollinator species

identified were foraging both on wild flowers and on the crop. Flower strips were mainly visited by wild pollinators (i.e. hoverflies and solitary bees), while strawberry flowers proved more attractive to honey bees and bumble bees, indicating their preference towards uniform and mass flowering over diverse resources. Despite the higher rate of wild flower visits, the study indicates a dispersal of pollinators from the flower strips to neighbouring crops rather than attracting and retaining them (Ganser et al., 2018). However, fully exploiting the potential of floral resources requires optimising their distribution in fields to counteract the appearance of sites excluded from their impact. In contrast, Hodgkiss et al. (2019) found no benefit to pollination services from interplanting of *Coriandrum sativum*, *Myosotis arvensis* or *Mentha arvensis* within covered strawberry crop. Companion plants reduced the number and diversity of functional groups of strawberry flower visitors compared to the control without flower treatments. Nevertheless, when taken together for strawberry and companion plants, the number of flower visitors was higher in *C. sativum* and *Mentha arvensis* plots. The number of fertile strawberry seeds was lower in the *Mentha arvensis* combinations than in the control. Floral treatments had no effect on marketable yield. The study shows that an increase in pollinator activity in fields with flower resources does not necessarily translate into improved pollination services. It is even possible for pollinating insects to be distracted by intercrops, but this may not result in a decrease in crop yield.

Establishing flower strips along the edges of sunflower fields did not produce consistent results. There were, however, some trends towards an increase in pollinator insect activity over the years following the establishment of the flower strips or an increase in seed productivity. Pollinator visitation rates to the crop flowers as well as sunflower productivity seemed to decrease with distance from the flower strips. The beneficial effect of the practice was more pronounced in a heterogeneous and flower-rich landscape context (Mota et al., 2022).

On smaller farms with diverse crop production profile, flower visitation by bees, pollination or yield of squash and sunflower did not vary with distance (20-180 m) from flower strips (Delphia et al., 2022).

Flower strips located 20 m away from the entrances to polytunnels increased the abundance of pollinating insects on strawberries by 25% on average. The main group of pollinating insects were bumblebees (67%), which responded most to the flower treatments. Hoverflies were slightly more abundant in treated crop polytunnels than in the no-strip control. Honey bees were observed less frequently in the treated crops than in the control crops, but this species was poorly represented in the overall pollinator population (Feltham et al., 2015).

Flower strips accumulated greater wild bee species richness, but on a whole-farm scale there were no significant differences in the abundance and diversity of these insects between sites with or without floral amendments. In one of the two years of the study, the flower strips significantly increased the fruit count of strawberry and squash plants, used as pollination indicators in the study. Moreover, the abundance and diversity of wild bees strongly decreased on farms where honey bee hives were maintained, resulting in poorer fruit set. This effect was not mitigated by the presence of the flower strips, suggesting that they might be not sufficient measure to prevent competition between honey bees and wild pollinators in agricultural landscapes (Angelella et al., 2021).

Wildflower strips in inter-rows of sweet cherry orchards grown under polytunnels increased the frequency of visits to cherry flowers by pollinators, as well as their abundance and diversity out of the crop blooming period. However, this did not result in higher fruit set (Mateos-Fierro et al., 2023).

Floral enhancements of implementing *Cajanus cajan* as double-sided strips on field margins and *Tagetes erecta* as intercrop in moringa cultivation increased the abundance and species richness of bees, wasps, flies, butterflies and flower visitors in general, reducing pollination deficit, thus resulting in improved pollination and increased fruit yield and quality (Dhandapani et al., 2024).

The presence of hedgerow trees in agricultural landscapes had a greater effect on the abundance and diversity of larger moths than grass-covered strips (Merckx et al., 2009).

Hedgerows at the edge of a pear orchard supported the population of managed *Osmia* spp. bees, as confirmed by analysis of mason bee-collected pollen and the frequency of hedge flower visits (Belien et al., 2021).

The presence of hedgerows, through increased pollinating insect activity, had a beneficial effect on fruit quality parameters of strawberries grown nearby. The hedgerows increased fruit weight and size, as well as the proportion of marketable yield. The surrounding habitat was important – hedgerows connected to forest were more effective in promoting pollination services than isolated hedgerows (Castle et al., 2019).

Hedgerows on the edges of apple orchards attracted a higher abundance and diversity of wild bees. There was no spillover effect; on the contrary, the presence of the hedgerow reduced the

population of wild bees in adjacent orchards, but without any negative impact on yield or fruit quality (Bishop et al., 2023).

Management of hedgerows on agricultural land reduced the abundance of bumblebees (Byrne & delBarco-Trillo, 2019).

Naturally growing hedgerows did not differ in their value for wild bees from hedgerows artificially planted with native shrub and tree species (Clausen et al., 2022).

In agricultural landscape, no differences in the number of flower-visiting insects were found between hedgerows and winter cereal crops (Couthouis et al., 2023).

Hedgerows promoted wild bee species diversity more strongly than grassland areas. A positive correlation was found between habitat quality (including the proportion of flowering shrubs in hedgerows) and wild bee richness, but also a significant influence of landscape context. The population of bee fauna in the hedgerows was closer to agricultural fields than to woodland (Dan et al., 2017).

The 'Farming with alternative pollinators' (FAP) strategy proposed by Christmann & Aw-Hassan (2012) needs a separate comment. It combines the transformation of cropping systems to protect wild pollinators with an emphasis on clear economic benefits for producers. Due to its low cost, the initiative can also be implemented in developing countries. Actions under the FAP strategy focus primarily on within-farm diversification of crops (up to a dozen of different species intercropped, e.g. vegetables, herbs, medicinal plants, fruit shrubs, oilseeds) to ensure (i.) their complementary, promoting effects on wild pollinators; (ii.) support of beneficial insects by growing crops generating direct income from the sale of the yield. Consequently, the results on the implementation of the FAP solutions are discussed in the subsection on intercropping, as, despite other outlier practices such as nesting support or creation of wild hedgerows as pollinator corridors, this term seems to most accurately describe the production design of the FAP system.

In addition to an enhancement in pollinator diversity and abundance, an increase in the yield of cucumbers and sour cherries (Christmann et al., 2017) and melons (Bencharki et al., 2024)

produced under the FAP system was found. However, the boost in the pollinator population on a whole field scale did not affect the frequency of flower visits to broad beans (Sentil et al., 2022a) or melons (Bencharki et al., 2023) as main crops. Sentil et al. (2022b) confirmed the potential for insects to use a variety of FAP crops as forage sources, but pointed out the need to supplement the species composition with plants that are also good sources of pollen, the scarcity of which may be a limiting factor in this system.

Floral habitats covering 2% of land and 1 km of flowering hedgerow were estimated to suffice the needs of six common wild bee species (three species each of the genus *Bombus* and *Andrena*), as well as their reproduction and larval rearing (Dicks et al., 2015).

Nevertheless, Donkersley et al. (2023) point out not to overestimate the small scale habitat enhancements either, demonstrating that not only extensive and compact floral structures support pollinator populations, but also smaller and isolated patches. However, the beneficial effect of smaller floral patches was diluted in large-scale farms, retaining only local importance. This indicates the key role of optimising the size, distribution and density of smaller floral habitats in managing resources for pollinators within the farm.

ŻYWOPŁOTY?

Farming with alternative pollinators – osobny podrozdział w intercropping

Wstępnie pasy kwietne w alejkach sadów też do intercropping

Targeted mixtures

Podrozdział – landscape context

Organic vs. conventional farming system - podrozdział

Jak to też wpływa na zapylenie uprawnej, znaleźć, czy towarzyszące „oddają” tych zapyłaczy

JAK te rośliny towarzyszące wspierają zapyłaczy ??? np. pożytek poza okresem kwitnienia uprawy, bardziej zróżnicowane źródło, bardziej wartościowe itd.

Db o zróżnicowanie zapylaczy, bo różne warunki ich pracy

Takie zabiegi to jest przyciąganie (atrakcyjność floral resources), ale czy wzrost populacji?

Carreck i Williams 1999 — niektóre gatunki produkują pyłek bez nektaru, inne jedno i drugie

W ogóle preferencje poszczególnych grup zapylaczy – można osobny rozdział

Szemat przedstawiający popularność poszczególnych rodzin w mieszankach kwiatnych wg źródeł ?

Kwestia lokalizacji pasów kwiatnych (obrzeża, regularnie w centrum) – możliwość zgromadzenia zapylaczy na obrzeżu i pogłębienia problemu spadku ich liczebności w centrum pola – cytowany tu Campbell et al. (2017a) za [Kohler et al., 2008](#), [Morandin and Kremen, 2013](#)

SKUPIĆ SIĘ NA MOŻLIWOŚCIACH ZWIĘKSZANIA LICZBY I RÓŻNORODNOŚCI OWADÓW ZAPYLAJĄCYCH W ROLNICTWIE I OGRODNICTWIE

wild bees and honey bees utilise different flowering resources within agricultural landscapes, where wild bees were tightly associated with semi-natural habitats while honey bees were mainly recorded from mass-flowering crops (Rollin et al. 2013).

Pas kwiatny w sadzie traktować jako śródplon inter-cropping

Nevertheless, our results are in a line with previous studies suggesting that such spillover effects may differ across taxonomic or functional groups of insects (Albrecht, Duelli, Müller, Kleijn, & Schmid, 2007; Balzan et al., 2016; Blitzer et al., 2012).

Czy odnotowany w jakichś badaniach wzrost plonu został bezpośrednio powiązany ze zapyleniem? → możliwe przecież inne oddziaływania, np. mniej szkodników. Poza tym, nie wszystkie gatunki roślin uprawnych wyraźnie reagują na obecność owadów zapylających

Solutions validated in temperate climates to support pollinator populations and crop pollination have also been tested in tropical agroecosystems..... dać przykłady, moringa, awokado, mango

Brak pełnej wersji artykułów:

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ARTICLE IN PREPARATION

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Supplementary material to the grant report of 9 June 2024

Grant details

Grantee name: Gerard Podedworny

COST action no.: CA21134

Grant no.: E-COST-GRANT-CA21134-614dc773

Grant title: The effect of companion plants on pest and beneficial insect population in greenhouse tomato production

Host institution: Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Lisbon, Portugal

Supervisor: Prof. Elisabete Figueiredo

This is to supplement the information in the previously submitted report with statistically processed data.

The total number of insects from the Ichneumonidae superfamily caught during May-November 2023 was 1078. Of these, 713 (66%) were Ichneumonidae, while the Braconidae family was represented by 365 (34%) of the specimens caught. This gives an interesting ratio between the two families of Ichneumonidae: Braconidae = 2:1, indicating a population of twice as many representatives of the family Ichneumonidae as Braconidae.

Figure 1. Evolution of the mean catch of ichneumonoids, in all eight Malaise traps, throughout the sampling season

Statistical analysis did not reveal significant differences among the catches on the different sampling dates or between the two greenhouses (t-test or Mann-Whitney non-parametric test were used, analyzing separately each sampling date) (Figure 1), but there were significant differences between the average number of ichneumonoids caught between trap 6

and traps 3 and 4 (GLMM with repeated measures, binomial distribution, type II Wald chi-square, mean comparison with Tukey test with Bonferroni correction) (table 1). Traps 3 and 4 were placed outside greenhouse A, between a wall and the greenhouse, in an area with some naturally occurring vegetation, and trap 6 was placed in the corridor between two greenhouses with soil not covered in vegetation and close to a road. This difference has to be taken into account in the analysis of the results obtained in Spring and Summer 2024 after the installation of the plant based infrastructure.

Table 1. Mean (\pm standard error) of the abundance of ichneumonoids caught in the different Malaise traps (different letters in the right-hand column indicate significant differences between the mean values, using the Tukey test ($p < 0.05$) with Bonferroni correction).

trap	Ichneumonoidea (mean \pm SE)
MT1	37.7 \pm 9.2 ab
MT2	44.0 \pm 20.1 ab
MT3	52.7 \pm 11.8 b
MT4	91.3 \pm 57.0 b
MT5	32.3 \pm 5.9 ab
MT6	17.7 \pm 9.0 a
MT7	31.3 \pm 6.6 ab
MT8	21.3 \pm 6.3 ab
χ^2	19.49
p	<0.01